

SPECIFIC INTERPRETATION OF HAND SOMATISM IN UZBEK FOLKLORE

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Annotation: this article reflects on the image of hand somatism in Uzbek folk songs. An artistic interpretation of such compounds as “putting henna on the hand”, “let the hand tie”, “Whip My Hand”, “broom of my hand”, the content of poetic images associated with the hand, the role of the hand in expressing the idea of the song is discussed in the song.

Keywords: hand, neck, metonymy, tajnis, “hand whip”, “hand broom”.

In Uzbek folk songs, expressions related to the human body organ form a significant part. The hand is the most important body member of a person, and in folk songs images associated with it, figurative compounds have arisen. Each image in the song, each medium serves to illuminate the idea of the song, to express the state of the lyrical hero:

If I lay on the White Moon,
The moon is in my bosom,
Sighed I open my eyes,
The hand is on my neck. (20-b).

The scratching of the hand on the neck is a sign of a warm attitude, affection. In this place, the creator refers to the person of two persons at once by using hand and neck somatisms together: one - a lover who owns a hand, and the other - a mistress who owns a neck . This is achieved on the basis of metonymy. There is another variant of the same song:

Three apples that gave semolina,
All three are in my bosom.
Sleeping and waking up,
Yor's hand is on my neck. (26-b)

It seems that there is a change in the three lines of this song, but there is no change in the verse of the last somatic composition. Sometimes it is popularly called “my hand broom”, in the sense of serving, not avoiding service. But there is also the phrase “whip my hand”, which is used to mean intimidating by beating something or someone:

Unless the rain is heavy,

Drop by the House.

I miss the crack,

My foot is a horse, my hand is a whip. (27-b)

Indeed, in the top four, it is hinted that the hand will whip the horse. The song uses both foot and hand somatism. It is pointed out that the leg runs like a horse, and the hand falls like a whip, as the lover of a lover who misses his own leg rides through them. It can be further said that while sometimes asov does not have a whip in his hand when riding, the vosuta that encourages the horse to walk, he does not have a foot on two of the horse's heels and urges him to walk with his hand, beating his jaw as if he had a whip. This realistic landscape image is taken as a basis in the song.

Don't take your door,

Water apples passing through the solution.

Nine apples in each hand

Is there a message from our house? (42 p.)

The word "solma" in the song means ariq in the Khorezm dialect. In this song, the name of the fruit with the verb to take through the words Apple tajnis art

formed. In this, attention is paid to the fact that the Apple is nine, and again it is nine in each hand, for a total of eighteen grains. So, the total amount of apples is eighteen, through which a hidden hint is made that yor is eighteen years old. In songs connected through the cults of productivity, fruit trees can be associated with the ideas of the family, children with a certain edge of meaning. Musakulov commented. (221-b) in this song, the Apple is an immature maid.

My ring in my hand turns three,

The child will fantasize if he sees us,

Don't dream, boy, I'll go myself,

I will set fire to the enemies' souls. (123 P.)

The three rotations of the ring on the hand, which means that it is a sign that it has come to the hand big. Through this, the mistress is ironic about the size of a lover. It is in this sense that the word boy is being used in place of the word boy and it is revealed that he is fantasizing, that is, hesitating, that he is afraid of people's Gossip. Therefore, the mistress expresses her willingness not to fear a guy in love with her, to be bold, not to hesitate, to put herbs on the souls of those who are enemies of themselves.

When Yorimnan went out into the field and hunted Crows,

I cut a branch out of a red flower and lay it down on the hand.
Red rose branch yordan ginam
Ildam not run out of the House. (149 P.)

The song references the enrichment of yor's hand with a branch of a red rose. Without the ability to attach a branch to a hand, the bruised yore could not be caught and stored.

I write in my hand Irgyliga,
Amateur hair to a long Beauty.
Give you your father who did not give you
Let him buy you, he is a thousand sheep.(168 P.)

The phrase 'hand recording' used in the song is associated with the concepts of slope taking, loving approach. In this place, this phrase also expressed the concept of going with longing.

In Uzbek folk songs, expressions, poetic images, migrations associated with hand somatism are directed to a certain goal in their essence. Such expressions in lyrical songs, spoken either in love or in the language of a mistress, serve mainly to brightly and vividly reflect the motives of love.

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